

Flat-Plate Collector Design with Differential Temperature Controller for PV/T Applications

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Abstract: Flat plate solar collector is mostly used for low-temperature solar systems. To raise the temperature of passing fluid (water) from system, a solar flat plate collector is used for. In present work, flat plate collector with concentrator was designed using proposed design for construction of PV/T water collector as discussed by other researchers. The performance of hybrid PV flat plate collector with V-shaped concentrator was investigated. Irradiance verses water temperature at certain view angle was numerically simulated and experimentally investigated. It is evident from the results that the efficiency of flat panel absorber was in accordance with the reported results. We observed that the temperature of 11 Kg of water rose from 20°C to 48°C. Finally, the result of efficiency verse differential temperature reveals that the efficiency slightly decreases as the temperature gradient per irradiance $(T_f - T_a)/I_c$ increases

Key words: Photovoltaic, View Angle, Flat Plate Collector, Efficiency.

INTRODUCTION The solar energy is one of the richest available renewable energy resources on earth. A photovoltaic cell is used to convert solar energy into electricity and heat works as a solar thermal system. Photovoltaic (PV) cells. A photovoltaic cell has more contribution in electricity generation than heat production [1]. When sun rays fall on the PV cell, a part of the energy are used to generate electricity while the rest of excess heat accumulates in the cell, from which the PV cell temperature goes on increasing and as a result it in turn decreases the efficiency of cell [2]. This excess heat energy can be reaped from PV cell, which also maintained the cell efficiency and use harvest heat in various applications [3]. Photovoltaic Thermal hybrid technology gives solution to this problem by lowering temperature and in turn giving hot water. The idea of this impinged technology PV panel and thermal collector was given by Kern and Russel in 1978 which gives us highly effective results for power and heat generation [4]. The cooling

system design or absorber design of PV/T hybrid system highly influences both thermal and electrical efficiency [5]. Absorber collector modules are placed under PV cell in such way that when water passes through it, it pulls its heat towards itself, which lowers its temperature and in return increases its efficiency. Based on water flow various notable absorber collector designs include direct flow, oscillatory flow, serpentine flow, web flow, spiral flow, parallel and modified serpentine parallel flow. It is simulated to create absorber design in which one has to maintain the system in view of overall efficiency. Based on the simulation, it can be said that spiral flow design is better in terms of its foremost cell efficiency (11.98%) and thermal efficiency (50.12 %) [5]. Mass flow rate, water inlet temperature, number of covers, absorber to fluid thermal conductance, PV cell packing factor, collector length and duct depth; these are the parameters that are kept in mind when designing absorber module [6]. Some of the collector designs are covered and some are kept without glazing. The downside covering PV/T collector is

that it raises the temperature because it is difficult to extract heat and doing so is tantamount to taking a risk [7]. Unglazed collector is good in that it exists heat as by-product at a very low temperature. Heat exchanger is used in contact with PV i-e thermal insulation and dry adhesive resins in case of unglazed collector. Photovoltaic Thermal Hybrid system (PV/T) is categorized in two types; Conventional PV/T which includes example of air-based PV/T and water-based PV/T technology and second one is advanced PV/T in which we have PV/T with nanofluids, Heatpipe-based PV/T collectors and PCM – based PVT collectors [8]. Water collector designs include 2D and 3D simulation models developed on the basis of energy performance analysis. For the production of indoor hot water, the model of single cover sheet and tube is proposed as one of the excellent models. Uncovered PVT/w collector is suggested for heating water at a low temperature. [9].

The idea to simultaneously produce heat and electricity is not innovative. It dates back to the time when both solar thermal and PV technologies were first known. Efforts aimed at reducing the size of the collector and making the system cost-effective are being made. Since the PV/T technologies being immature these efforts went somewhat absorptive. The most commonly used design for PV/T collector was a sheet and tube design come from flat-plate solar collector design [10]. Solar cells can be cooled via water and air using as coolant, which results in enhancing its electricity yield, but the best design is if we can re-use the heat that came out if it [11]. Cooling is more effective by using water compared with the use of air as cooling fluid which did not gave a result of better heat transfer due to low density, specific heat and thermal conductivity. Thus, better performance can be achieved by using water instead of air as cooling fluid due to higher heat extraction. Using concentrator type PV/T or C-PV/T as an alternate to flat-plate collector is adept to raise the solar cell's radiation intensity. Here we illustrate the design of concentrator and water-cooling collector based on simulation design, results and experimental work. A water-based hybrid collector formed by extruded aluminum alloy with polycrystalline PV module on a flat-box type thermal absorber was constructed and tested. This flat-box thermal collector is fixed to the back of PV module. It finally rises a final temperature of water up to 48°C through routine operation, is knowing to favor highly effective heat transfer and durability.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND PROCEDURE

Polycrystalline Solar PV module of 30- watt capacity is used for experimental work. For the study of thermal behavior of PV module, comparison between following has been made.

1. PV module with Thermal collector incorporated with concentrator
2. PV module with Thermal collector and without concentrator

Design configuration of collector

The PV module with collector is made by using aluminum sheet having total working area of 201,300 mm². The aluminum sheet is cut into 2-pieces each of length 610mm and width 330mm. The two aluminum sheets are connected by rectangular strips with a spacing of 4mm, which gives rectangular box like structure as shown in figure.

Design configuration of concentrator

The concentrator model comprises of cavity box of dimension 650mm in length and 350mm in width is made from a light weight wood where the solar panel is fixed. The cavity box is extended by a side bar by 2 inches in order to provide support for reflector sheets at 60° vertex angle for maximum absorption of solar radiation on the collector plate.

Fig (1) The diagram representation of collector module (a) front side of module using inlet and outlet for passing water (b) backside.

Simulation System

Ray tracing software is used for representing the technique by computer programming for solar concentrating system. Ray tracing is used logarithmically in the area where computer version exists. To calculate interaction between Solar radiation and concentrator in a computer procreate representation, ray tracing logarithm is designed. The basic purpose of ray tracing technique is extending out number of virtual rays into a solar concentrator during simulation. The rays are extending out from determined

x, y, z coordinate know as viewpoint and ray path is traced from viewpoint ray path is traced until it collides concentrator.

Fig (2) Simulation Design of Concentrator based hybrid PV Flat Plate collector.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 shows a solar concentrating system. It consists of virtual incident solar rays, reflector and absorber. Every solar ray has a position, starting point and direction which depends on the given angle of sun. Silver reflecting sheet is used as reflector. The absorber: Rectangular box shape is used as absorber, which is made responsible for 100 % absorption, placed in between two reflectors to absorb rays.

The Simulations of design with respect to view angle is demonstrated in Figure 3(a,b). It can be noticed that the maximum irradiance is obtained at view angle around 0-degree angle of vertical and horizontal axis as shown in Figure 3(b). The maximum irradiance of 1622 W/m² was recorded around 0 degree simulated view angle. The solar irradiance decreases with increase in view angle and thus the concentrated PV modules result in gradual decrease in efficiency of the device.

Fig (3) Irradiance Min: 1.5365e-009 W/m², Max:2392.7 W/m², Ave:1433 W/m², Total Flux:3.26 W, 9984 Incident Rays. The water temperature versus solar penal efficiency was recorded as shown in Figure 4. It was observed that

the solar penal efficiency increases with increase in water temperature up to 27°C. After that the penal efficiency gradually started decreasing with an increase in water

temperature. At water temperature 45°C, the penal efficiency reached to its lowest value of 10.3%. This Fig (4) A plot between water temperature and hybrid PV module efficiency is Inversely proportional to increasing water temperature.

Fig (4) A plot between water temperature and hybrid PV module efficiency.

The result of simulation is given in the form of plotted graph of irradiance versus view angle. The x-axis represents view angle whereas the y-axis is shows the irradiance (W/m²) for each measured angle. The maximum irradiance flux was measured at 0° which decreases with increase in view angle.

Fig (5) A graph between solar irradiance and simulation view angle.

Fig (6) A graph between efficiency curve and differential temperature.

Graph shows collector efficiency versus Differential Temperature, using data. The efficiency of water-type thermal collector was found to be about 40-60%. It shows that differential absorber temperature slightly influences collector efficiency which is uniform.

CONCLUSION

In this work, the performance of hybrid PV flat plate collector with V-shaped concentrator was investigated. Irradiance versus water temperature at certain view angle was numerically simulated and experimentally investigated. It is evident from the results that the efficiency of flat panel absorber was in accordance with the reported results. We observed that the temperature of 11 Kg water raised from 20°C to 48°C. Finally, the result of efficiency versus differential temperature reveals that the efficiency slightly decreases as the temperature gradient per irradiance $(T_i - T_a)/I_c$ increases.

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